

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Personal Development Potential of the German Language Textbook for the Institute of Railway Transport

Larissa I. Sereda* (a)

(a) *Zabaikalsky Institute of Railway Transport — a branch of Irkutsk State Transport University.*
672040, Chita, Magistralnaya St. 11
sereda_larissa@mail.ru

Abstract

Humanization and humanitarianism of education has always been and should remain the fundamental principles of educational activity of University and pedagogical activity of a teacher. This statement is especially relevant in the era of ubiquitous digitalization, which has penetrated in different spheres of life and life of any individual. Today it is humanitarianism that is recognized as a counteracting power to digitalization, which, at the same time, cannot be perceived as something hostile to society and people. Only humanitarianism, with its humanitarian nature and meaning of everything that happens, can protect society from social catastrophe and even greater immersion in material values. This paper postulates the need to apply the principle of humanitarianism in the development of a foreign language textbook for technical Universities, which allows the textbook to provide potential for personal development. The personal development potential of a foreign language textbook is aimed at developing the general culture of students, which is understood as the social, intellectual, spiritual development of an individual. The article examines current trends in understanding the essence of the principle of humanitarianism and its implementation in educational institutions of the country, studies the requirements for the design of a foreign language textbook. The purpose of the article is to analyze the personal development potential of a German language textbook written for students of the University of Railway Transport and to formulate recommendations for the development of foreign language textbooks for technical Universities on the principles of humanitarianism. The main approach in the study is the empirical method, which helps to prove that a foreign language textbook, developed on the principles of humanitarianism, contains personal development potential, and, in particular, can contribute to the development of the general culture of students. The practical significance of the research is the formulation of requirements for foreign language textbooks for technical Universities based on the application of the principle of humanitarianism.

Keywords: humanitarianism, foreign language, textbook, general culture.

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* Corresponding author. E-mail: sereda_larissa@mail.ru

Introduction

The relevance of the study is determined by the need to design foreign language textbooks for technical Universities, which aimed not only at the development of foreign language communicative competence required by the Federal State Educational Standard, but also at the development of the general culture of student's personality. We associate this need with the increased illiteracy of students and their lack of a common culture. We believe that the reasons for these phenomena are the digitalization of many spheres of human life and the active use of various forms of distance learning. In the context of restrictive measures caused by the pandemic, negative aspects are already observed in the education system. They are as follows: depersonalization of the educational process, the increasing immersion of students in virtual communications, formalism in assessing students' knowledge, commercialization of knowledge, oversaturation of the Internet space with educational materials characterized by pragmatism and the absence of a humanitarian component, risks of decreased motivation for learning, loss of intrinsic value of knowledge, unification and primitivization of the content of education and training (Dozhdikov, 2020; Gafurov, Ibragimov, Kalimullin & Alishev, 2020; Mikhailov & Denisova, 2020). To prevent such technocratic realities, it is necessary to turn to such educational principles as humanization and humanitarianism. Traditionally, the humanization of education is understood as filling with humanistic ideas all spheres of activity of an educational institution, harmonizing the processes taking place at the University, creating favorable conditions for the development and disclosure of students' abilities. Humanization in the higher education system is aimed at both the harmonious development of the student's personality and the holistic professional development of teachers. Humanization of education is realized through implementation of humanitarianism. Humanitarianism is a principle of education, which can be guided by every teacher in his teaching activities. Humanitarianism is the filling with humanitarian knowledge of any academic discipline, a personal-activity approach in teaching, tolerance within the educational process, the creation of harmonious relations within the teaching and student collective, the formation of personal and professional culture as a way of life, familiarizing students with spiritual and moral and cultural values through various methodological approaches, forms and methods (Dyachkova, Novgorodtseva & Tomyuk, 2020; Stukalova, Kudryavtseva, Ganaeva, Fadeyeva, Osyanova & Natochy, 2018). The principle of humanitarianism can be used by teachers in the development of foreign language teaching aids.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to analyze the personal development potential of the published German language textbook for the students of the Institute of Railway Transport. We are aimed at listing

recommendations for the development of foreign language textbooks for technical Universities based on the application of the principle of humanitarianism. The object of the research is humanitarianism as a principle implemented in the development of foreign languages textbooks for students of a technical University. The subject of the research is a German language textbook, developed on the basis of the principle of humanitarianism and aimed at developing the general culture of the student's personality. Research hypothesis - a foreign language textbook for students of a technical University should contain a potential that contributes not only to the formation of foreign language communicative competence, but also to the development of a general culture of an individual. This requirement can be realized through the application of the principle of humanitarianism. Research tasks: 1) to analyze modern approaches to the essence of the principle of humanitarianism; 2) study the requirements for a foreign language teaching materials; 3) to analyze the personal development potential of a German language textbook, its potential for the development of students' general culture; 4) on the basis of the experiment, formulate the requirements for the development of a foreign language textbook for technical Universities based on the principle of humanitarianism, which contains the potential for the development of student's general culture.

Literature review

It is a common knowledge that in the 70s of the last century, humanitarianism was viewed exclusively as the inclusion of humanitarian disciplines in the curricula of technical Universities. With the time going on, both among researches and practicing teachers, an opinion has emerged that humanitarianism should be considered much broader and, first of all, as opposed to technocratism - a negative phenomenon in the educational process of a University associated with the formation of certain functions, decrease in the importance of humanitarian knowledge, denial of the human principle in the educational and educational processes, ignoring the process of educating students of spiritual, moral and cultural values. According to the technocratic paradigm of education, the student is considered as an object of pedagogical influence and is treated according to unified methods of the prescribed standards and norms. The principle of humanitarianism, first of all, is intended to prevent the development of a technocratic approach in the educational process of a technical University. With the humanization of technical education, conditions can be created for interdisciplinary education. Social studies and human arts are considered fundamental, including in-depth study of a foreign language, thus leading to a change in stereotypes as well as adoption of humanitarian culture and communicative competence. (Kitova, 2018).

In the process of studying at a technical University, it is not enough for a future engineer to gain knowledge in some humanitarian disciplines; it is important and necessary for teachers to cultivate in him such qualities as humanity, tolerance, respect for history and eternal spiritual values, the desire for self-

development. There is a unanimous opinion of researchers that the implementation of the principle of humanitarianism involves an individual centrality of the entire educational process, his spiritual and moral development, the growth of the creative potential of students, filling technical disciplines with humanitarian knowledge.

In 2018, on the basis of the Tyumen Industrial University, the International Scientific and Methodological Conference "Humanitarianization of Engineering Education: Methodological Foundations and Practice" was held, during which professionals from nine flagship Russian Universities discussed the methodological foundations of the humanitarianism of the professional and cultural environment of a modern technical University. At the conference, the program "Humanitarianization of Engineering Education of a Flagship University" was presented, which allows a University to become an innovative platform both for the development of the regional community and for the development of a system of technical training in Russian Universities in the aspect of creating a dialogue space for flagship Universities on the issue of humanizing the educational process (Tolstoukhova, Stavetskaya & Vasilieva, 2018). The urgent need for interactive educational technologies and non-authoritarian types of relations was also noted, which is the core of the humanitarianism in education and the humanization of the educational environment. The emphasis was given to strengthening the humanitarian component of technical and engineering education, which is the basis for the development and formation of general cultural components of the future specialist and consists in the axiologization of the educational process. In addition to the theoretical analysis of the process of humanitarianism in engineering education, methods of its implementation were proposed, such as the introduction of relevant humanitarian disciplines, the integration of humanitarian and special disciplines through their contextual interpenetration, the formation of supra-professional competencies and professionally important qualities of undergraduates, the participation of the student community in social projects aimed at solving local social problems of the city and the region (Tolstoukhova, Stavetskaya & Vasilieva, 2018).

No less important is the opinion that the humanization of the educational process primarily concerns the sphere of relations, and the humanitarianism in education determines the way of thinking and understanding the final result of education within the framework of cultural relations (Tarasenko, 2018). Thanks to this definition, the so-called "humanization" of any relations within the educational process is possible: between the teacher and the student/students, between teachers, between the administration of the University and the teaching staff. Also, there is a potential for harmonization of the ultimate goals of the educational process - the development of graduates' professional competencies that are necessary for successful employment and further development, upbringing of a culturally and spiritually developed personality, capable of analyzing the events taking place around him or her, developing in new working and

living conditions, striving to harmonize relations within the society.

In connection with the process of digitalization of all spheres of life in our country, there is a cultural conflict, overcoming of which could be realized through humanitarianism in higher education. That is why humanitarianism is interpreted as a buttress and one of the beginnings of the formation of a digital society and digital culture (Kuznetsova, 2019). Scientists should prove and philosophically comprehend the idea of humanizing higher education in a new social and cultural context.

Humanitarianism seems to us as the teacher's pedagogical activity aimed at creating harmonious relations within the educational process, the teacher's use of those techniques, forms and methods that will fully contribute to both the implementation of educational goals and the formation of correct spiritual and moral values, the development of the general culture of the student.

We assume that the principles of humanitarianism should be used by teachers when developing foreign language textbooks at a technical University. As it is known, teaching materials are educational aids designed to expand, deepen and for better assimilation of knowledge provided by the curriculum. At first glance, it seems that for a technical University, a textbook should contain professionally oriented texts aimed at the formation of knowledge in a specialty in a foreign language, but we consider this way to be technocratic. Among the requirements for textbooks and teaching aids in a foreign language, the following are put forward:

- when developing a foreign language textbook, a semiotic approach can be used, which is based on signs, symbols and other images to be explained, described in a foreign language, which largely leads to the rapid assimilation of certain phrases (Wenninger & Kiss, 2013);
- a foreign language textbook for professionally oriented learning includes a system of functions: managerial, communicative, informational, developmental and educational, functions of vocational orientation, self-control, self-education (Fedorova, 2014);
- a foreign language textbook should contribute not only to the development of grammar and vocabulary of a foreign language, but also to the formation of intercultural communicative competence, that is, the ability to effectively use a foreign language, taking into account the socio-cultural background of the communicative situation (Sándorová, 2016);
- work on the textbook includes the study of special literature that deals with the structure of specialized textbooks, scientific and methodological literature on the main problems of the methodology of teaching

foreign languages, generalization of modern trends in methodological experience in the field of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic educational institutions. Also, a prerequisite is the identification of interdisciplinary connections between the profile discipline and the discipline "foreign language". A mandatory requirement for textbooks in a foreign language for non-linguistic specialties is a systematic and consistent presentation of the material. Lexical and grammatical exercises are of a communicative nature, tasks are aimed at developing oral skills of reproductive foreign language communicative competence (Smirnova, Choporova & Serostanova, 2017);

- a foreign language textbook aimed at developing intercultural communicative competence should optimize the teaching of a foreign language; a new concept of the textbook is needed, which would determine the intercultural specifics of its system and structure, thereby forming an idea of learning foreign language in the format of situational modeling of intercultural communication (Tareva, Shchepilova & Tarev, 2017);

- in the textbook, it is necessary to reflect the interaction between different cultures through texts and exercises, which will lead to the development of intercultural consciousness and intercultural competence (Wenwei & Jianfei, 2019);

- English language textbook should contribute to students' sustainable social and environmental development, that is, such a textbook should include topics that reflect socially significant problems in people's lives and form their active life position aimed at saving the planet and preserving its natural and cultural wealth; tasks in such a textbook should be problematic, that is, put students in a position of reasoning and reflection in a foreign language on vital social and environmental topics (Mohammadnia & Moghadam, 2019).

We believe that the requirements put forward by modern teachers for the development of foreign language textbooks and teaching aids are relevant, necessary, aimed at the formation of professional skills, the development of a broad outlook on life, the upbringing of the qualities and personality traits of students that are important for life in society. In our opinion, a foreign language textbook for technical Universities cannot be only professionally oriented, because we see this approach as narrow and does not meet the modern requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard for the development of foreign language communicative competence. Such a textbook should contain the potential for the development of the student's personality, his general culture, the upbringing of spiritual and moral values.

Methodology

The purpose of the study is to experimentally prove the potential of a German language textbook, the development of which was based on the principles of humanitarianism, to develop general culture among students of a technical University.

The following research methods were used to test the hypothesis of the research and to solve the assigned problems:

- theoretical: analysis of modern scientific works on humanitarianism, analysis of the requirements for the developers of a foreign language textbook, analysis of the personal development potential of a German language textbook;
- empirical: pedagogical observation, interviews, survey, testing.

The study was based on the Full-time Department of the Zabaikalsky Institute of Railway Transport, a branch of the Irkutsk State Transport University. For the experiment, two full-time student groups were selected. The first (control) group in a foreign language class studied according to a textbook developed according to the traditional academic scheme, which assumes the presence of the main text, vocabulary for the text, tasks for translating words, phrases and sentences, reading and translating the text, answering questions for the text. The second (experimental) group studied according to the textbook, which was based on the principles of humanitarianism, as well as aimed at developing the general culture of students. The experiment involved 24 students.

The experiment consists of 3 stages. At the first stage (September-December 2020), a foreign language was taught in the control and experimental groups using the teaching aids selected for this stage of training according to the calendar plan developed on the basis of the working curriculum of the discipline. At this stage, pedagogical observation and a survey were carried out at the end of the stage. At the second stage (December 2020), testing and interviews were conducted in both groups, which helped to draw conclusions about the advisability of using the principles of humanitarianism in the development of a textbook. The third stage of the experiment (January 2021) included the analysis of the results obtained and the formulation of recommendations for the development of a foreign language textbook for technical Universities based on the use of the principles of humanitarianism, containing the potential for the development of the student's general culture.

Results

For over 20 years, humanitarianism has been the basis of our pedagogical activity, which is expressed in

filling with the humanitarian meaning of any method, technique, technology used in teaching the discipline "Foreign language". During our experiment in the control group we used a textbook developed according to the academic traditional scheme. This manual consists of texts, a lexical list is given for each text, then there are exercises for consolidating vocabulary with reading and translation, exercises for drilling grammatical rules in the form of translation of sentences, tasks for translating the text and answering questions to the text. Quite often, textual material and exercises do not coincide with lexical and grammatical material. In the experimental group, we used a textbook, the development of which was based on the principles of humanitarianism: focus on the student's personality, his needs and interests, his cultural upbringing and development, increasing motivation to learn a foreign language, filling with the content that would help students strive for new knowledge, including the study of a foreign language. Thus, in 2016, we issued the textbook "German for Specialist and Bachelor Degree Students", recommended by the Far Eastern Regional Educational and Methodological Center (FE REMC) as a textbook in the discipline "Foreign Language" for students of all specialties and areas of training of Universities in the region. The textbook is compiled in accordance with curriculum "Foreign language". It is aimed at developing students' language communicative competence. The practical requirement is the formation of speaking skills sufficient for communicating with native speakers, reading and understanding German texts of a general, educational and scientific character, as well as for further studying the German language within the framework of the specialty. The textbook was created on the basis of carefully selected textual material on the problems of modern science and technology. The main criterion for the selection of texts was the informative value of the texts and their relevance to the interests of students of technical Universities.

The textbook consists of five chapters, each of which includes sections such as "Grammatik: Theorie und Praxis", "Lexik", "Lesen und Sprechen". The section "Grammatik: Theorie und Praxis" presents theoretical material on certain grammatical topics with written and oral exercises. In this section, special attention is paid to teaching the construction of a colloquial phrase in German. In the "Lexik" section, vocabulary is trained and drilled on the main topic of the chapter. The vocabulary helps you understand the content of the main text, which is presented in the next section "Lesen und Sprechen". In this section, students read the main text and do oral and/or written exercises. At the end of each chapter, a lexical and grammatical test is given, which is checked by the teacher. The chapters are designed to develop skills in various types of reading, speaking, translation and writing. The grammar of the manual covers basic topics such as the formation of tense forms of the German language, the formation and use of the active and passive voice, the formation of degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs, the formation of numbers, modal verbs, infinitives with *zu* and without *zu*, modal constructions. The texts for additional reading are compiled for the organization and conduct of independent and individual learning.

Lesson structure:

- 1) grammatical material, including grammatical exercises, the purpose of which is to revise the school grammar minimum, as well as introduction and drilling of new grammar material. The block of grammar exercises is based on everyday lexical material familiar to students at this stage of training;
- 2) lexical material, which includes a list of words from the topic; lexical pre-text exercises, in which lexical units from a list of words are introduced, systematized and drilled. The block of vocabulary exercises contains testing exercises;
- 3) material for reading and speaking includes a system of texts intended for teaching reading as a type of speech activity and major types of reading (scanning, searching, familiarizing and in-depth reading), as well as pre-text and post-text exercises. The texts are provided with exercises for practicing various techniques for extracting semantic information. One of the main forms of information processing is considered to be an annotation and an abstract. Therefore, a number of exercises are aimed at teaching fast search and comprehension of information, a selective approach to the content of the text and fixing information in a concise form. In addition, the exercises for the core text of the lesson are aimed at developing oral speech skills;
- 4) vocabulary and grammar test for checking the acquired knowledge.

In the following we will give an example from the textbook looking at the organization of the first chapter, which is called “Die Ausbildung der Fachkräfte an den Hochschulen für Bahnwesen” (Training of specialists in railway Universities). The section "Grammatik: Theorie und Praxis" includes 3 tasks that precede the theory of grammar related to the study of the present tense *Präsens*. So, first, students are invited to read and understand the monologues of university students about their studies, then it is necessary to supplement sentences with words from these dialogues, supplement the dialogues with special interrogative words and supplement the dialogues with personal pronouns. Thus, the learners are led to the study of the grammar material. The theoretical material includes the rules for the formation of the present tense and tables with the conjugation of German verbs. Root vowels and verb endings are highlighted in different colors for better understanding of the rules. Further go exercises for mastering grammatical rules, they contain tasks for the substitution of correct endings, the formation of correct verb forms in accordance with the person and number. Tasks to formulate a question to a given sentence and vice versa are effective when an answer is given to a question with a missing verb form, etc. The grammatical section is followed by the “Lexik” section, which includes a list of words from the following text. Here are the tasks for choosing the correct meaning of a word from four options, choosing synonyms and antonyms, choosing the

correct word from three in sentences. This is followed by the section “Lesen und Sprechen” with the main text, preceded by phrases that are not included in the list of current vocabulary to facilitate understanding of the content of the text. After reading the text, students are asked to make sentences from words scattered in a chaotic order, as well as discuss the text in pairs based on the proposed questions. At the end of the study of the chapter, it is proposed to carry out a lexical and grammar test. The following chapters contain topics such as "Die Trends der Entwicklung der Hochausbildung in der Richtung des Bolognaprozesses in Europa" (Trends in Higher Education in the Mainstream of the Bologna Process in Europe), "Deutsche Wissenschaftler und Erfinder" (German Scientists and Inventors), "Die bekannten deutschen Nobelpreisträger "(Famous German Nobel Prize Winners)," Verkehr und Verkehrsmittel "(Transport and vehicles). Thus, we see the relevance of the selected topics for students of a technical university and the potential for the development of a general culture of the personality of an individual student.

Pedagogical observation of the first stage of the experiment allowed us to see that the students in the control group quickly lost interest in the lesson, the tasks were often delayed in time, the students were heavily involved in the tasks, the students who were not involved in the task were bored and not engaged. Observation of the students in the experimental group revealed a lively and genuine interest in the tasks, the formulation of the tasks made it possible to organize work in pairs/groups, which caused a good mood and inspiration when completing the tasks. The students were sincerely happy in the case of the correct formulation of a phrase in a foreign language. It should be noted that the teaching aid used in the experimental group has the formulations of tasks, tables highlighted in different colors, therefore it was perceived by the students with great interest. At the end of the first stage of the experiment, a survey was conducted in the groups, the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Statement	Control Group (12 respondents)	Experimental Group (12 respondents)
1. The textbook – interesting and useful.	2	12
2. The textbook – boring and useless.	10	0
3. The textbook inspires my desire to learn new things.	4	12
4. The textbook develops my general culture.	5	12
5. The textbook has improve my foreign language proficiency.	6	12

Thus, the textbook, developed using the principles of humanitarianism, arouses great interest among students, the work with it contributes to the development of general culture and to the increase in the level of proficiency in a foreign language, and also helps to optimize the educational process.

At the second stage of the experiment, interactive testing was carried out in each group on the institute's platform. Testing included tasks on the studied material: closed and open-type tasks, tasks for correspondence, tasks for correct sequence. The results of testing carried out on the platform of the institute represent the percentage of tasks completed and the level of competence formed. The test results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Indicators	Control Group (12 respondents)	Experimental Group (12 respondents)
The percentage of the completed tasks (%)	69,00%	94,00%
The level of the developed competence (the number of students)	Minimum	2
	Basic	3
	High	7

The test results showed a higher percentage of tasks completed in the experimental group than in the control group. In the control group, 50% of students have mastered the minimum level of competence, the basic level of competence is observed at 30%, a high level of competence is formed at 20% of students. In the experimental group, we observe the following results: 10% of the students found the minimum level of competence, 20% - the basic level, and 70% of the students reached a high level, which indicates the effectiveness of the textbook developed on the basis of the principles of humanitarianism.

Also, the interviews were conducted in both groups, during which the results were summed up, the expectations of the students from the educational process, the advantages and disadvantages of the textbook were discussed, the wishes of the students to the developers of the textbook were expressed. Moreover, it was proposed for each group to get acquainted with the textbook of another group. The interviews showed that the students of the control group were dissatisfied with the structure of the textbook (often the number of tasks was different in each Unit, the tasks were not clearly stated) and the tasks aimed mainly at translating from one language to another. They found it difficult to say with confidence that after the end of

the semester, their foreign language proficiency improved. The participants in the control group positively assessed the textbook from the experimental group: structure, formulations of tasks; the interior view of the textbook was highly appreciated. The students of the experimental group expressed their complete satisfaction with the educational process, noted an increase in interest in a foreign language, positive changes regarding the enrichment of their general culture, spoke in favor of continuing to study the foreign language. In the experimental group, the textbook of the control group received only a satisfactory mark.

At the third stage of the experiment, the analysis of the results obtained allows us to say the following:

- the selection of texts and lexical material in the traditional textbook as a whole corresponded to the specialty, but it did not create conditions for the formation of at least basic competence and the development of general culture among students, did not ensure the conduct of the educational process at the proper effective level; did not create favorable conditions for the formation of positive motivation to learn a foreign language and did not increase interest in learning the language further;
- the textbook, developed using the principles of humanitarianism, made it possible to realize the set goal - the formation of linguistic communicative competence and the development of the general culture of students. Thanks to the refusal of the authors from translation tasks and introduction of communicative language and speech tasks, it became possible to develop speaking skills, increase interest and form positive motivation for learning the foreign language.

Thus, we can formulate requirements for the development of a textbook on a foreign language in a technical University, which we divide into two groups: axiological and didactic.

We attribute the following to axiological requirements: when developing a textbook in a foreign language, the developer must be based on the principles of humanitarianism, which proclaims the saturation of pedagogical activities with a humanitarian sense, in focusing on the needs and interests of students, searching for effective techniques, methods and technologies in teaching a foreign language, creating harmonious conditions for the formation of linguistic communicative competence, the upbringing of the personality of the future graduate and the development of a general culture, the creation of conditions for the development of the student's desire to further study a foreign language.

The didactic requirements include the following: it is necessary to observe the unity of the educational, developmental and educational functions of the textbook; correspondence of the textbook material to its purpose; deliberately elaborated structure of the textbook, logical connections between texts and assignments; the orientation of the text material on the development of the student's personality and the

enrichment of his general culture; development of communicative language and speech tasks, as well as case-studies that require analysis and reflection in a foreign language; complete rejection of translation assignments; the equal quantity of tasks in each section / chapter.

Thus, the carried out experiment confirmed the hypothesis about the advisability of applying the principles of humanitarianism in the design of a foreign language textbook. Such textbooks contribute to the upbringing and development of general culture among students, increasing the motivation for learning a foreign language, filling the educational process with a humanitarian sense.

Discussions

In contemporary conditions of development of the state, we consider humanization and humanitarianism to be the key educational principles of every higher educational institution in the Russian Federation, the fundamental principles in the activities of every teacher. On the one hand, we see interest in these principles from some researchers and Universities of the country. Interuniversity conferences are held on the problems of humanization and humanitarianism of education, more and more interesting and high-quality in foreign language textbooks are being developed, but on the other hand, as the practice shows, we observe more and more technocratic attitudes of University administration towards teachers, students, to the pedagogical process as a whole, which, first of all, affects the quality of education. Unfortunately, mature teachers continue to develop textbooks according to an outdated traditional scheme that do not meet modern requirements and interests of students, therefore, it is necessary to pay close attention to this problem on the part of heads of departments, methodological councils of Universities and clear explanatory work. We need a constant appeal to the principles of humanization and humanitarianism in the connection with the increased digitalization of the society and all spheres of life. There is danger of formation of such a society whose members will not be able to develop even after graduating from any educational institution.

Conclusion

The results of this research contribute to the understanding of the essence of the principles of humanitarianism, demonstrate the extreme importance of the implementation of the principles of humanitarianism both in the educational activities of all Universities and in the pedagogical activities of each teacher. The humanitarianism of education is designed to resist any technocratic phenomena in the educational process, to fill every type of pedagogical activity with a humanitarian sense, including the development of teaching aids in all the disciplines. It is the humanitarianism of education that will contribute to the harmonization of relations between the digitalization process and the society. Thanks to the application of the principles of humanitarianism, a foreign language textbook can contain personal

developmental potential, which will enhance student's general culture. In the course of experimental work, we proved the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language with the help of a textbook developed on the principles of humanitarianism. At the end of the experiment, requirements were formulated for foreign language teaching aids for a technical University based on the application of the principles of humanitarianism.

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